

Creative Magic Squares: Single Letter Representations

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Abstract

*This paper brings magic squares of orders 3 to 10 in terms of **single letter**. In case of orders 8 and 9 there are two possibilities, i.e, one as normal magic square and another as **bimagic** square. In this situation, the magic squares are written in both the possibilities. In case of order 10, again there are also two possibilities. One without any blocks, and second as blocks of order 8, divided again in four blocks of order 4, known as **block-bordered** magic squares. Writing in terms of single digit "**a**", where **a** can be **1, 2, ..., 9**. For the orders 3 to 9, few exercises are also written.*

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1 Introduction

In [1, 2] we wrote numbers in terms of single digits. Below are few examples of symmetric representations of few numbers:

$$5 = \frac{11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99 - 9}{9 + 9}$$

$$6 = \frac{11 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33 + 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{44 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66 + 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{77 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99 + 9}{9 + 9}$$

$$55 = \frac{111 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{777 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 - 9}{9 + 9}$$

$$56 = \frac{111 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 + 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666 + 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{777 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 + 9}{9 + 9}$$

Motivated by this idea, instead working for each digit separately, we can work with a **single letter "a"**, for example,

• Running-Type

$$5 := (aa - a)/(a + a)$$

$$6 := (aa + a)/(a + a)$$

$$55 := (aaa - a)/(a + a)$$

$$56 := (aaa + a)/(a + a)$$

$$561 := (aaaa + aa)/(a + a)$$

$$666 := aaa \times (aa + a)/((a + a) \times a)$$

$$925 := (aaaaa - aa)/(aa + a)$$

$$1089 := (aaaa - aa - aa)/a$$

$$1991 := (aaaaaa/aaa \times (a + a) - aa)/a$$

$$2020 := (aaaaa - a)/aa \times (a + a)/a$$

$$2035 := (aaaa - a)/(a + a + a) \times aa/(a + a)$$

$$5000 := (aaaaa - aaaa)/(a + a).$$

$$4477 := (aaa/(a + a + a) \times aa \times aa)/(a \times a)$$

$$4999 := (aaaaa - aaaa - a - a)/(a + a)$$

• Fraction-Type

$$5 := \frac{aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$6 := \frac{aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55 := \frac{aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$56 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$561 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$666 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$786 := \frac{\left(\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{a} - a\right) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$925 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a}$$

$$1089 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$1991 := \frac{\frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} \times (a + a) - aa}{a}$$

$$2020 := \frac{\frac{aaaaa - a}{aa} \times (a + a)}{a}$$

$$2035 := \frac{\frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} \times aa}{a + a}$$

$$4477 := \frac{\frac{aaa}{a + a + a} \times aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$4999 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - a - a)}{(a + a)}$$

$$5000 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa)}{(a + a)}$$

$$122988 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

where $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, and $aa = 10 \times a + a$, $aaa = 10^2 \times a + 10 \times a + a$, etc.

Few numbers are written as double fraction. We can write them as single fraction too. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 786 &:= \frac{((aa + a) \times aa - a \times a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 1991 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a) - aa \times aaa}{aaa \times a} \\
 2020 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a \times aa} \\
 2035 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times (a + a)} \\
 4477 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

The full work is from 1 to 11111 numbers, written in two different ways can be seen in author's work [3, 4]. For more details refer [7].

2 Single Digits Magic Squares

In recent works [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14], the author worked with **magic squares**. These works include **block-wise** and **block-bordered** magic square from order 3 to 47. Summarized work on magic square can be seen in [15]. Below are basic magic squares of orders 3 to 10, and their representations in terms of single letters. Few exercises are also written. Similar kind of work for single digit can be seen in citeta16.

2.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

Let's write the above magic square in terms of single letter "a" by choosing the representations values from the Appendix 4.

Example 2. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 3 given in Example 1 is written in single letter "a":

$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$
$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 3 is given by

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

Exercise 1. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following magic square of order 3 in terms of single letter "a":

			66
21	33	12	66
13	22	31	66
32	11	23	66
66	66	66	66

2.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 3. Let's consider a **pandigonal** magic square of order 4 given by

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

Example 4. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given in Example 3 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 4 is given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

Exercise 2. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following pandiagonal magic square of order 4 in terms of **single letter "a"**:

		110	110	110	110
	23	34	11	42	110
110	12	41	24	33	110
110	44	13	32	21	110
110	31	22	43	14	110
	110	110	110	110	110

2.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 5. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 given by

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

Example 6. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 given in Example 3 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 5 is given by

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

Exercise 3. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following **padiagonal** magic square of order 5 in terms of **single letter "a"**:

		165	165	165	165	165
	11	22	33	44	55	165
165	43	54	15	21	32	165
165	25	31	42	53	14	165
165	52	13	24	35	41	165
165	34	45	51	12	23	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165

2.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 7. Let's consider a magic square of order 6 given by

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

Example 8. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 6 given in Example 8 is written in single letter "a":

$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$
$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 6 is given by

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{aaa}{a}$$

Exercise 4. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following **padiagonal** magic square of order 6 in terms of **single letter "a"**:

						231
11	65	64	63	12	16	231
56	22	54	23	25	51	231
46	45	33	34	42	31	231
36	32	43	44	35	41	231
21	52	24	53	55	26	231
61	15	13	14	62	66	231
231	231	231	231	231	231	231

2.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 9. Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 is given by

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

Example 10. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 given in Example 9 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$
$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 7 is given by

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - aa)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

Exercise 5. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following **padiagonal** magic square of order 7 in terms of **single letter "a"**:

		308	308	308	308	308	308	308
	11	22	33	44	55	66	77	308
308	65	76	17	21	32	43	54	308
308	42	53	64	75	16	27	31	308
308	26	37	41	52	63	74	15	308
308	73	14	25	36	47	51	62	308
308	57	61	72	13	24	35	46	308
308	34	45	56	67	71	12	23	308
	308	308	308	308	308	308	308	308

2.6 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 8

Example 11. Let's consider a **pan magic square** of order 8 is given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

Example 12. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 given in Example 11 is written in single letter "a":

$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$
$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa}{a} + \frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a} + \frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a}$
$\frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 8 is given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

In this case the blocks of order 4 are also **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{aaa + aa + aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

Example 13. Let's consider a **pandiagonal bimagic** square of order 8 given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	16	41	36	5	27	62	55	18	260
260	26	63	54	19	13	44	33	8	260
260	1	40	45	12	22	51	58	31	260
260	23	50	59	30	4	37	48	9	260
260	38	3	10	47	49	24	29	60	260
260	52	21	32	57	39	2	11	46	260
260	43	14	7	34	64	25	20	53	260
260	61	28	17	56	42	15	6	35	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, the above magic square of order 8 is **bimagic** with **bimagic** sum $Sb_{8 \times 8} := 11180$. Each 2×4 blocks is with equal sum entries as of magic square, i.e., 260

Example 14. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the above **pandiagonal and bimagic** magic square of order 8 given in Example 13 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$
$\frac{(aa+a+a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times aa}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times(aa-a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times aa}{a\times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times(aa+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a} + \frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa\times aa-a\times a)}{(a+a)\times a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$
$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times aa}{a\times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a)\times aa}{(a+a)\times a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 8 is given by

$$S_{8\times 8} := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

In this case the blocks of order 2×4 are of same sum as of magic square. Moreover, the above magic square is also **bimagic**. Its **bimagic** sum is given by

$$Sb_{8\times 8} := \frac{(aaaa + aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

Exercise 6. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following **padiagonal** magic square of order 8 in terms of **single letter "a"**:

		396	396	396	396	396	396	396	396
	45	58	11	84	35	68	21	74	396
396	14	81	48	55	24	71	38	65	396
396	88	15	54	41	78	25	64	31	396
396	51	44	85	18	61	34	75	28	396
396	46	57	12	83	36	67	22	73	396
396	13	82	47	56	23	72	37	66	396
396	87	16	53	42	77	26	63	32	396
396	52	43	86	17	62	33	76	27	396
	396	396	396	396	396	396	396	396	396

2.7 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

Example 15. *Let's consider a pandiagonal magic square of order 9 is given by*

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
369	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Example 16. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the above **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 given in Example 15 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a} + \frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a}{a}$
$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{(aa-a-a-a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$
$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$
$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$
$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa-a-a}{a+a}$

In this case the **magic sums** of magic square of order 9 is given by

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

In this case, the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares (sum of only rows and columns) with equal **semi-magic** sums.

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

Example 17. Let's consider a **bimagic** square of order 9 given by

									369
1	18	23	35	40	48	60	65	79	369
33	38	52	55	72	77	8	13	21	369
62	67	75	6	11	25	28	45	50	369
27	5	10	49	30	44	74	61	69	369
47	34	42	81	59	64	22	3	17	369
76	57	71	20	7	15	54	32	37	369
14	19	9	39	53	31	70	78	56	369
43	51	29	68	73	63	12	26	4	369
66	80	58	16	24	2	41	46	36	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, the above magic square of order 9 is **bimagic** with **bimagic** sum $Sb_{9 \times 9} := 20049$. Each 3×3 block is with equal sum entries as of magic square i.e., 369.

Example 18. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 9 given in Example 18 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times(aa-a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times(aa+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(aa\times aa-a\times a)}{(a+a)\times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a)\times aa - a}{(a+a)\times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a)\times(aa+a)}{(a+a)\times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a)\times aa}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$
$\frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa\times(a+a)}{(a+a+a)\times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa+aa}{a} + \frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a)\times aa}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa\times(a+a)}{(a+a+a)\times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$
$\frac{(aa+aa+a)\times(a+a)+a\times a}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a)\times(aa-a-a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a)\times aa - a+a}{(a+a)\times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$
$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a)\times aa-a\times a}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$
$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a)\times(a+a+a) - a}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{(aa+a)\times aa}{(a+a)\times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a)\times(aa-a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a)\times(a+a)}{a\times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a)\times(a+a+a)}{a\times a}$

In this case, the above magic square is also **bimagic**. The magic and **bimagic** sums are given by

$$S_{9\times 9} := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

and

$$Sb_{9\times 9} := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times aa \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

Exercise 7. Using the representations given in Appendix 4, write the following **padiagonal** magic square of order 9 in terms of **single letter "a"**:

		495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495
	34	88	43	39	81	45	32	86	47	495
495	48	33	84	41	35	89	46	37	82	495
495	83	44	38	85	49	31	87	42	36	495
495	54	18	93	59	11	95	52	16	97	495
495	98	53	14	91	55	19	96	57	12	495
495	13	94	58	15	99	51	17	92	56	495
495	74	68	23	79	61	25	72	66	27	495
495	28	73	64	21	75	69	26	77	62	495
495	63	24	78	65	29	71	67	22	76	495
	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495	495

2.8 Magic Squares of Order 10

Example 19. *Let's consider a magic square of order 10 is given by*

										505
1	80	65	97	39	22	48	86	53	14	505
98	12	9	66	90	74	55	33	41	27	505
47	81	23	79	16	35	94	60	62	8	505
70	57	88	34	2	91	29	15	76	43	505
84	99	52	11	45	68	73	7	30	36	505
13	38	44	10	77	56	82	21	95	69	505
75	46	40	83	28	19	67	92	4	51	505
59	24	96	42	61	3	20	78	37	85	505
26	5	17	58	93	50	31	64	89	72	505
32	63	71	25	54	87	6	49	18	100	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

Example 20. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 10 given in Example 19 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} - \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaaa+aaa}{aa+a+a}$	$\frac{(aa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$
$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$
$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$
$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a}$

In this case the **magic sum** of magic square of order 10 is given by

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa + aa}$$

2.9 Block-Bordered Magic Squares

Below are two different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 based on magic squares of order 8 given in Examples 11 and 13.

Example 21. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88
89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12
11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90
96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5
1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100
93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8
7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94
95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

In this case the 4 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 202$. The magic square of order 8 is with magic sums $S_{8 \times 8} := 404$

Example 22. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 10 given in Example 21 is written in **single letter "a"**:

$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a+a)}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a+a+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a+a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$

Example 23. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 with inner part as **bimagic** square of order 8 is given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92
13	34	59	54	23	45	80	73	36	88
89	44	81	72	37	31	62	51	26	12
11	19	58	63	30	40	69	76	49	90
96	41	68	77	48	22	55	66	27	5
1	56	21	28	65	67	42	47	78	100
93	70	39	50	75	57	20	29	64	8
7	61	32	25	52	82	43	38	71	94
95	79	46	35	74	60	33	24	53	6
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10

In this case, the magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with **magic** and **bimagic** sums as $S_{8 \times 8} := 404$ and $Sb_{8 \times 8} := 23132$.

Example 24. According to representations given in Appendix 4, the magic square of order 10 given in Example ?? is written in single letter "a":

$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (aa+aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{(a+aa+a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+aa+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aaa+aa+aa+a)}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+aa+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+a}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+aa+a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(a+aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a+a}$
$\frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+a}{a+aa+aa+a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+aa+a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a) \times (a+aa+a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$	$\frac{(aaa+aa+aa+a)}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a-a-a}{a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa}{a+aa+a} + \frac{a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa+aa}{aa+aa+a}$
$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+aa+a) \times a}$	$\frac{(aa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a+a) \times a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a}$
$\frac{aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a-a-a}{a}$	$\frac{a+a+a}{a}$	$\frac{aaa-aa-a}{a}$	$\frac{aa-a}{a}$

In this case, the magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with **magic** and **bimagic** sums are given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} = 404 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$Sb_{8 \times 8} = 23132 := \frac{(aaaa - aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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- **Single Letter Representations**

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● **Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares**

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4 Appendix: Single Letters Representations

Within the magic squares we have used total 1 to 100 numbers for the magic squares of orders 3 to 10. The magic sums vary according to each magic square. Any way the maximum number is 505. Below are representations of numbers from 1 to 1000 in terms of single letter. More details can be seen in author's work [3, 7].

Through out it is understood that for all

$$aa := 10 \times a + a;$$

$$aaa := 10^2 \times a + 10 \times a + a;$$

$$aaaa := 10^3 \times a + 10^2 \times a + 10 \times a + a,$$

... ..

$$\text{where } a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= \frac{a}{a} \\
 2 &:= \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 3 &:= \frac{a+a+a}{a} \\
 4 &:= \frac{a+a+a+a}{a} \\
 5 &:= \frac{aa-a}{a+a} \\
 6 &:= \frac{aa+a}{a+a} \\
 7 &:= \frac{aa-a-a-a-a}{a} \\
 8 &:= \frac{aa-a-a-a}{a} \\
 9 &:= \frac{aa-a-a}{a} \\
 10 &:= \frac{aa-a}{a} \\
 11 &:= \frac{aa}{a} \\
 12 &:= \frac{aa+a}{a} \\
 13 &:= \frac{aa+a+a}{a} \\
 14 &:= \frac{aa+a+a+a}{a} \\
 15 &:= \frac{aa+a+a+a+a}{a} \\
 16 &:= \frac{aa+a+a+a+a+a}{a} \\
 17 &:= \frac{aa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 18 &:= \frac{(aa-a-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 19 &:= \frac{aa+aa-a-a-a}{a} \\
 20 &:= \frac{aa+aa-a-a}{a} \\
 21 &:= \frac{aa+aa-a}{a} \\
 22 &:= \frac{aa+aa}{a} \\
 23 &:= \frac{aa+aa+a}{a} \\
 24 &:= \frac{aa+aa+a+a}{a} \\
 25 &:= \frac{aa+aa+a+a+a}{a} \\
 26 &:= \frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 27 &:= \frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 28 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a} \\
 29 &:= \frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 30 &:= \frac{(aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31 &:= \frac{aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a} \\
 32 &:= \frac{aa+aa+aa-a}{a} \\
 33 &:= \frac{aa+aa+aa}{a} \\
 34 &:= \frac{aa+aa+aa+a}{a} \\
 35 &:= \frac{aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a} \\
 36 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 37 &:= \frac{aaa}{a+a+a} \\
 38 &:= \frac{aaa}{a+a+a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 39 &:= \frac{(aa+a+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 40 &:= \frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a} \\
 41 &:= \frac{aaa+aa+a}{a+a+a} \\
 42 &:= \frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 43 &:= \frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 44 &:= \frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 45 &:= \frac{(a+a+a+a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 46 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 47 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 48 &:= \frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a} \\
 49 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a+a} \\
 50 &:= \frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} \\
 51 &:= \frac{aaa-aa+a+a}{a+a} \\
 52 &:= \frac{aaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 53 &:= \frac{aaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 54 &:= \frac{aaa-a-a-a}{a+a} \\
 55 &:= \frac{aaa-a}{a+a} \\
 56 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a} \\
 57 &:= \frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\
 58 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 59 &:= \frac{(aa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 60 &:= \frac{(aa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a+a) \times a} \\
 61 &:= \frac{aaa+aa}{a+a} \\
 62 &:= \frac{(aaa+aa+a+a)}{a+a} \\
 63 &:= \frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 64 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 65 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 66 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} \\
 67 &:= \frac{aaa+aa+aa+a}{a+a} \\
 68 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} + \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 69 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 70 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 71 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 72 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} \\
 73 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 74 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} \\
 75 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 76 &:= \frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 77 &:= \frac{(aa-a-a-a-a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 78 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa}{a} \\
 79 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a} \\
 80 &:= \frac{(aa-a-a-a) \times (aa-a)}{a \times a} \\
 81 &:= \frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a} \\
 82 &:= \frac{(aa-a-a) \times (aa-a-a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 83 &:= \frac{(aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 84 &:= \frac{(a+a+a+a) \times (aa+aa-a)}{a \times a} \\
 85 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a} \\
 87 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a-a}{a} \\
 87 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-aa-a-a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 89 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 90 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a}{a} \\
 91 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a} \\
 92 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 93 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 94 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa}{aa + a + a} \\
 95 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 96 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 97 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 98 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 99 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a}{a} \\
 100 &:= \frac{aaa - aa}{a} \\
 101 &:= \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 102 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{aa} \\
 103 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa}{aa} \\
 104 &:= \frac{aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 105 &:= \frac{aaa - aa + a}{a + a} \\
 106 &:= \frac{aaaa}{aa} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\
 107 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 108 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 109 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a}{a} \\
 110 &:= \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 111 &:= \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 112 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 113 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\
 114 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 115 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 116 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{(a + a) + aaa} \\
 118 &:= \frac{aa \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 119 &:= \frac{aa \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 120 &:= \frac{aa \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 121 &:= \frac{aa \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 122 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a} \\
 123 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a} \\
 124 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a)}{a} \\
 125 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a + a)}{a} \\
 126 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a + a + a)}{a} \\
 127 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\
 128 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a} + \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \\
 129 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 130 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 131 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 132 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 133 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa}{a} \\
 134 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\
 135 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\
 136 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 137 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa}{aa - a - a} \\
 138 &:= \frac{aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 139 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{aa - a - a - a} \\
 140 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\
 141 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 142 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 143 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 144 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 145 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\
 146 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\
 147 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 148 &:= \frac{aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 149 &:= \frac{aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 150 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 151 &:= \frac{[aaaa \times (a + a + a) - a \times aa]}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 152 &:= \frac{[aaaa \times (a + a + a) + a \times aa]}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 153 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 154 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 155 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a} \\
 156 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 157 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 158 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 159 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 160 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} \\
 161 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 162 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 163 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 164 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 165 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 166 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a}{a + a} \\
 167 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a}{a + a} \\
 168 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 169 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 170 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa - aa - a}{aa + a + a} \\
 171 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + a}{aa + a + a} \\
 172 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 173 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 174 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 175 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - aa)}{(aa + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 176 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 177 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 178 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 179 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa + aa)}{aa \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 180 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa + aa}{a} \\
 181 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa + aa - a}{a} \\
 182 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 183 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 184 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 185 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a} \\
 186 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 187 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 188 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 189 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 190 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 191 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 192 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa - a}{a} \\
 193 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(aa \times a) - aa} \cdot a \\
 194 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 195 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 196 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 197 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 198 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 199 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a)}{a} \\
 200 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 201 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 202 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 203 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 204 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 205 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 206 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 207 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 208 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 209 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 210 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a} \\
 211 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\
 212 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{aa - a}{a} \\
 213 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 214 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 215 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 216 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 217 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 218 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 219 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 220 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 221 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - a}{a} \\
 222 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa}{a} \\
 223 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a}{a} \\
 224 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 225 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 226 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 227 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 228 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 229 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 230 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 231 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 232 &:= \frac{aa \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 233 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa}{a} \\
 234 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a}{a} \\
 235 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\
 236 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 237 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 238 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a + a + a} - \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 239 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 240 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 241 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 242 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 243 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 244 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 245 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a)}{a} \\
 246 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 247 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 248 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 249 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 250 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a + a + a} \\
 251 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 252 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 253 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 254 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 255 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 256 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\
 257 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\
 258 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 259 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 260 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 261 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$262 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$263 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$264 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$265 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$266 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$267 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$268 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$269 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$270 := \frac{(aaa - a - a - a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$271 := \frac{(aaa - a - a - a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$272 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$273 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$274 := \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$275 := \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$276 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$277 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$278 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$279 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$280 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$281 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + a)}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$282 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa) \times (a + a + a)}{(aa + a + a) \times a}$$

$$283 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa - a)}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$284 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$285 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$286 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$287 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$288 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$289 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa - aa)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$290 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$291 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$292 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$293 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$294 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$295 := \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$296 := \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$297 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$298 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$299 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$300 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$301 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$302 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$303 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$304 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$305 := \frac{(aaa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$306 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$307 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$308 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$309 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$310 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$311 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$312 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$313 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$314 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$315 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$316 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$317 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$318 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$319 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$320 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$321 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$322 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$323 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$324 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$325 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$326 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$327 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$328 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$329 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$330 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$331 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$332 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a}{a}$$

$$333 := \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$334 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a}{a}$$

$$335 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$336 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$337 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$338 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$339 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$340 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$341 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$342 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$343 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$344 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$345 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$346 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$347 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 348 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 349 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a} \\
 350 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 351 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{(aaa - a - a)}{a} \\
 352 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 353 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 354 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa - a}{a} \\
 355 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa}{a} \\
 356 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 357 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\
 358 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{((a + a) \times (a + a)) + aaa} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 359 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a} \\
 360 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 361 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 362 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 363 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 364 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 365 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 366 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 367 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa + a)}{a + a + a} \\
 368 &:= \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 369 &:= \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 370 &:= \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} \\
 371 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a + a + a} \\
 372 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 373 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a + a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 374 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a + a} \\
 375 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 376 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a + a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 377 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a + a} \\
 378 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a} \\
 379 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 380 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 381 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa - a}{a + a + a} \\
 382 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a + a + a} + \frac{dracaa}{a} \\
 383 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a} \\
 384 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 385 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 386 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 387 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 388 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 389 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a + a} \\
 390 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 391 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\
 392 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 393 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 394 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 395 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 396 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 397 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 398 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 399 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 400 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 401 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 402 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 403 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 404 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 405 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 406 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 407 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 408 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 409 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 410 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 411 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa}{a + a + a} \\
 412 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a + a} \\
 413 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 414 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 415 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 416 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a - a}{a} \\
 417 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a} \\
 418 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 419 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 420 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 421 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 422 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 423 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 424 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa + aaa}{a} \\
 425 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa + aa}{a} \\
 426 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a} \\
 427 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa + aa)}{((a + a) \times (a + a + a))} \\
 428 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 429 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 430 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 431 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 432 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 433 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\
 434 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\
 435 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\
 436 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 437 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 438 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 439 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa}{a + a} \\
 440 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 441 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 442 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 443 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - a}{a} \\
 444 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 445 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a + a} \\
 446 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 447 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 448 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 449 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 450 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a + a} \\
 451 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 452 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 453 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 454 &:= \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 455 &:= \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa}{(a \times a) + aa} \\
 456 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 457 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 458 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 459 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 460 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 461 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - aaaa - aa}{a + a} \\
 462 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\
 463 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times a}{((aa + a) \times (a + a))} \\
 464 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 465 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa - a - aaaa}{a + a} \\
 466 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 467 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 468 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 469 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 470 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 471 &:= \frac{aaaa - a + aaaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aa}{aa} \\
 472 &:= \frac{aaaa - a + aaaa + aa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aa}{aa} \\
 473 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - aa}{a \times a} \\
 474 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - aa - a}{a \times a} \\
 475 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - aa - a - a}{a \times a} \\
 476 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(aa \times (a + a + a))} \\
 477 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{((a + a) \times (aa + a + a + a))} \\
 478 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - a + a + a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 479 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - a + a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 480 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 481 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 482 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 483 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a}{aa + aa + a} \\
 484 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\
 485 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 486 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 487 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a + a}{a + a} \\
 488 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 489 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a + a} \\
 490 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a}{a + a} \\
 491 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a) - a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 492 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 493 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a} \\
 494 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a} \\
 495 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a + a} \\
 496 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 497 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 498 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 499 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a}{a + a} \\
 500 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a} \\
 501 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 502 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 503 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 504 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 505 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa + aa} \\
 506 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\
 507 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 508 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a + a + a + a}{aa + aa} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 509 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a + a + a + a + a}{aa + aa} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 510 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa \times (a + a))} \\
 511 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa}{a + a} \\
 512 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 513 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa - a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 514 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa + a + a - a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 515 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 516 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + aa + a}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 517 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 518 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 519 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{aaa+a}{a} \\
 520 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a+a+a) \times a} + \frac{aaa+a+a}{a} \\
 521 &:= \frac{(aaaa+aa) \times (aa-a)}{(aa+aa) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 522 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa}{a+a} - \frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a} \\
 523 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa-a-a}{a+a} - \frac{aaa}{a+a+a} \\
 524 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa}{a+a} - \frac{aaa}{a+a+a} \\
 525 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+a+a+a) \times (aa+aa-a)}{a \times a} \\
 526 &:= \frac{(aaaa+aaaa) \times (a+a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aaa+aa}{a} \\
 527 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a} \\
 528 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+aa+aa) \times (aa+a)}{a \times a} \\
 529 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+a) \times (aa+aa+a)}{a \times a} \\
 530 &:= \frac{aaaa-a-a}{aa+aa-a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 531 &:= \frac{aaaa-a-a}{aa+aa-a} + \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 532 &:= \frac{(aaa+aa+aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} \\
 533 &:= \frac{(aaa+aa+a) \times (aa+a+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} \\
 534 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-aa-aa-aa+a}{a+a} \\
 535 &:= \frac{(aaa-a-a-a-a) \times (aaa-a)}{(aa+aa) \times a} \\
 536 &:= \frac{(aaa+aa+aa+a) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} \\
 537 &:= \frac{aaaa-aaa}{a+a} + \frac{aaa}{a+a+a} \\
 538 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-aa-aa-a-a}{a+a} \\
 539 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-aa-aa}{a+a} \\
 540 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-aa-aa+a+a}{a+a} \\
 541 &:= \frac{(aaaa-aa) \times aa}{(aa+aa) \times a} - \frac{aa-a-a}{a} \\
 542 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa+a)}{((aaa+aa+a) \times (a+a))} \\
 543 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-aa-a-a-a}{a+a} \\
 544 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 545 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} - \frac{aa}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 546 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-aa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\
 547 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} - \frac{aa-a-a}{a} \\
 548 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-a-a-a-a}{a+a} \\
 549 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa-a-a}{a+a} \\
 550 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa}{a+a} \\
 551 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa+a+a}{a+a} \\
 552 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 553 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 554 &:= \frac{aaaa-a-a-a-a}{a+a} \\
 555 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} \\
 556 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} \\
 557 &:= \frac{aaaa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\
 558 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 559 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa}{a+a} - \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 560 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa-a-a}{a+a} \\
 561 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa}{a+a} \\
 562 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+a+a}{a+a} \\
 563 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+a+a+a+a}{a+a} \\
 564 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} + \frac{aa-a-a}{a} \\
 565 &:= \frac{(aaa+a+a) \times (aa-a)}{(a+a) \times a} \\
 566 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 567 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 568 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+aa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\
 569 &:= \frac{(aaaa+a) \times aa}{(aa+aa) \times a} + \frac{aa+a+a}{a} \\
 570 &:= \frac{(aaa+a+a+a) \times (aaa-a)}{(aa+aa) \times a} \\
 571 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+aa+aa-a-a}{a+a} \\
 572 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+aa+aa}{a+a} \\
 573 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+aa+aa+a+a}{a+a} \\
 574 &:= \frac{(aaa+aa+a) \times (aaa+a)}{(aa+a) \times (a+a)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 575 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+aa+a)}{(a+a+a+a) \times a} \\
 576 &:= \frac{(aaa+aa+aa+aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a+a) \times a} \\
 577 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+aa+aa+aa-a}{a+a} \\
 578 &:= \frac{aaaa+aa+aa+aa+aa+a}{a+a} \\
 579 &:= \frac{aaaa-aaa+a}{aa+aa-a-a-a} \\
 580 &:= \frac{aaaaa+aaaa}{aa+aa-a} - \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 581 &:= \frac{aaaaa+aaaa}{aa+aa-a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 582 &:= \frac{aaaaa+aaaa}{aa+aa-a} \\
 583 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a} + \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} \\
 584 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a+a+a} + \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} \\
 585 &:= \frac{(aaa+aaa+aa+a) \times (aa-a)}{(a+a) \times (a+a)} \\
 586 &:= \frac{(aa+aa+a) \times aa+aaa \times (a+a+a)}{a \times a} \\
 587 &:= \frac{aaaa-aa}{a+a} + \frac{aaa}{a+a+a} \\
 588 &:= \frac{(aa+aa-a) \times (aaa+a)}{(a+a+a+a) \times a} \\
 589 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 590 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{aa-a}{a} \\
 591 &:= \frac{(aaa+a) \times aaa}{(aa+aa-a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 592 &:= \frac{(aaa+a) \times aaa}{(aa+aa-a) \times a} \\
 593 &:= \frac{(aaa-a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{aa+a}{a} \\
 594 &:= \frac{(aaa-a) \times aa}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 595 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa+a)}{(aa+aa) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 596 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa+a)}{(aa+aa) \times a} - \frac{aa-a}{a} \\
 597 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a+a+a}{a} \\
 598 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} - \frac{a+a}{a} \\
 599 &:= \frac{(aaa-a-a) \times aa-a \times a}{(a+a) \times a} \\
 600 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} \\
 601 &:= \frac{(aaa-aa) \times (aa+a)}{(a+a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$602 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$603 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$604 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$605 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$606 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$607 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$608 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a)}{(aa + aa) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$609 := \frac{(aaa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$610 := \frac{(aaa \times aa - a \times a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611 := \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a + a}$$

$$612 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$613 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$614 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$615 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$616 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$617 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$618 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$619 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$620 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$621 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times aa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$623 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + aa + a + a)}{a + a}$$

$$624 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$625 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$626 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$627 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$628 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$629 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$630 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$631 := \frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} - \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$632 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$633 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$634 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$635 := \frac{aaa + aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$636 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{(aa + a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$637 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(aa + aa) \times aaa}$$

$$638 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + aa}{a}$$

$$639 := \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$640 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$641 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$642 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$643 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$644 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa + aa}{a}$$

$$645 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$646 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$647 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$648 := \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{df racaaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$649 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa + aa}{a}$$

$$650 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$651 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$652 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{aa} + \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$653 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$654 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$655 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$656 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$657 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$658 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$659 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$660 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$661 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$662 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$663 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$664 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$665 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$666 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$667 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$668 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$669 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$670 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$671 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$672 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$673 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$674 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$675 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$676 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$677 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$678 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$679 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$680 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$681 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 682 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 683 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 684 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a} \\
 685 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 686 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 687 &:= \frac{((aaaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) + aa + a} aa - a - a \\
 688 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 689 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 690 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 691 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 692 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 693 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a} \\
 694 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{aa - a - a - a} + \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a} \\
 695 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 696 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 697 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 698 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 699 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 700 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - aa)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 701 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 702 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 703 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 704 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 705 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - aa}{a} \\
 706 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{(aaa - aa + a)}{a} \\
 707 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 708 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times aa} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 709 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times aa} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 710 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 711 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 712 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 713 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 714 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 715 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 716 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 718 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\
 719 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 720 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 721 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 722 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 723 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{((a + a) \times a)} \\
 724 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times a \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 725 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 726 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 727 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + aa}{a} \\
 728 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 729 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 730 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 731 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 732 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 733 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 734 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 735 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 736 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a + a} \\
 737 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa - aa}{a + a + a} \\
 738 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{(a + a)}{a} \\
 739 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 740 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 741 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 742 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 743 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 744 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa - a}{a + a + a} \\
 745 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a} \\
 746 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 747 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 748 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 749 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 750 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\
 751 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 752 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - a - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a} \\
 753 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a} \\
 754 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 755 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 756 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 757 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 758 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 759 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 760 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 761 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$762 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$763 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - a - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$764 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$765 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$766 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$767 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$768 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$769 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a}{aa + a + a}$$

$$770 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$771 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$772 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$773 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$774 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$775 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$776 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$777 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$778 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$779 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a}$$

$$780 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$781 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa + aa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$782 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$783 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$784 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$785 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa + a}{aa + a + a + a}$$

$$786 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa + aa}{a}$$

$$787 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$788 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$789 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$790 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$791 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$792 := \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a \times a}$$

$$793 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$794 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$795 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$796 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$797 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$798 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$799 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$800 := \frac{(aa - aaa) \times (a - aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$801 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$802 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$803 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$804 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$805 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$806 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$807 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$808 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a}$$

$$809 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$810 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$811 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$812 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$813 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$814 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$815 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$816 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$817 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$818 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$819 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$820 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$821 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$822 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$823 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a) \times a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$824 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a) \times a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$825 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$826 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaaa - aa}{aa}$$

$$827 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + aaa}{a}$$

$$828 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + aaa + a}{a}$$

$$829 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$830 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa + aa}{a}$$

$$831 := \frac{(a - aaaa + a + a) \times (a - aa + a)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

$$832 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a}{aa + a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$833 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a}{aa + a}$$

$$834 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$835 := \frac{(aaa - aaaa - a - a) \times (a - aa)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

$$836 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$837 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$838 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa + aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$839 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$840 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$841 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$842 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$843 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$844 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$845 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aaa - aa \times (a + a)}{(aa - a - a - a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$846 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - a - a}{aa + a + a}$$

$$847 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa}{aa + a + a}$$

$$848 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$849 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$850 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$851 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$852 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa}{aa + a + a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$853 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa}{aa + a + a}$$

$$854 := \frac{aaaaa - aa + a + a}{aa + a + a}$$

$$855 := \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{aa + a + a}$$

$$856 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$857 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$858 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$859 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$860 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$861 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$862 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$863 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$864 := \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a \times a}$$

$$865 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$866 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$867 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$868 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$869 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$870 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$871 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$872 := \frac{(a - aa + a + a) \times (a - aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$873 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa}{aa + a + a + a}$$

$$874 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$875 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$876 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$877 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$878 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$879 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$880 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$881 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$882 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$883 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$884 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$885 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$886 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$887 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$888 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$889 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$890 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a}$$

$$891 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$892 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$893 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$894 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$895 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa}{a + (aa + a)}$$

$$896 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$897 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{aa}$$

$$898 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa}{aa}$$

$$899 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa}{aa}$$

$$900 := \frac{(aa - aaa) \times (a - aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$901 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$902 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$903 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$904 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$905 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$906 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a + a + a}{a}$$

$$907 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$908 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} - \frac{a}{a}$$

$$909 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$910 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$911 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$912 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$913 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$914 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$915 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$916 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$917 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$918 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$919 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$920 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$921 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$922 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$923 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a}$$

$$924 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - a}{aa + a}$$

$$925 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a}$$

$$926 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a}$$

$$927 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} + \frac{a}{a}$$

$$928 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{aa + a}$$

$$929 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{aa \times a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$930 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 931 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\
 932 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \\
 933 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a) \times a} - \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 934 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a) \times a} - \frac{a}{a} \\
 935 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a) \times a} \\
 936 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a}{aa + a} \\
 937 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + aa}{aa + a} \\
 938 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a} \\
 939 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a} \\
 940 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa) \times (aa - a)}{(aa + a + a) \times a} \\
 941 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + aa}{aa + a + a} \\
 942 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + aa}{aa + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 943 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 944 &:= \frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} - \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 945 &:= \frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} - \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} \\
 946 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 947 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa - aa \times aa}{(aa + a + a) \times a} \\
 948 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + aa}{aa + a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\
 949 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa} - \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} \\
 950 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aaa - aa)}{(aa + a) \times a} \\
 951 &:= \frac{((aaa + a + a) \times aaaa - aa \times a)}{((aa + a) \times aa)} \\
 952 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times (aaa + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\
 953 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - a}{aa} - \frac{aaa + a}{a + a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 954 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa} - \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} \\
 955 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa} - \frac{aaa - a}{a + a} \\
 956 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 957 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 958 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 959 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 960 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\
 961 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 962 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 963 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 964 &:= \frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a} \\
 965 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 966 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 967 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 968 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 969 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aa)}{(aa \times (aa + a))} \\
 970 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a} \\
 971 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa}{aa + aa + a} \\
 972 &:= \frac{(a - aaa + a + a) \times (a - aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 973 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a} \\
 974 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a}{aa} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a} \\
 975 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 976 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 977 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 978 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 979 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 980 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a} \\
 981 &:= \frac{(a - aaa + a) \times (a - aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 982 &:= \frac{(a - aaa + a) \times (a - aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a}{a} \\
 983 &:= \frac{(a - aaa + a) \times (a - aa + a)}{a \times a} + \frac{a + a}{a} \\
 984 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 985 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 986 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 987 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 988 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a} \\
 989 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa}{a} \\
 990 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a} \\
 991 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\
 992 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 993 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 994 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a} - \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \\
 995 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 996 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 997 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 998 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a}{a} \\
 999 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a}{a} \\
 1000 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$